

Economic analysis

Farmer participation and cost effectiveness of bulk fertilizer purchasing scheme in Sri Lanka

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To reduce fertilizer cost in rice production, a bulk fertilizer purchasing scheme (BFPS) was introduced in Hambantota, a major rice-growing district in southern Sri Lanka. This program promoted farmer groups to collectively purchase fertilizer at the wholesale level to avoid the higher retail prices.

We evaluated the degree of farmer participation in the BFPS and the cost effectiveness of the scheme. Sixty farmers were randomly selected and interviewed at the end of 1993-94 *maha* (wet) season.

About 70% of the farmers continued to buy fertilizer directly from retailers rather than through the scheme. Several factors accounted for this preference. Retailers grant credit that farmers commonly use. Many farmers have deviated from the standard fertilizer recommendation, which made estimating the bulk quantity a difficult task. Farmers typically apply fertilizer in three splits (basal and two topdressings) and prefer to buy small quantities as needed for a particular application. In the BFPS, farmers did not always receive fertilizer in time for application. In some instances, farmer organizations granted credit to facilitate participation in the BFPS, but borrowers did not settle the loans properly. Fertilizer purchased through the BFPS cost \$81.40/ha and on an individual basis, \$83.10/ha. The difference in cost was not statistically significant by t-test. All of these factors negatively affected participation in the scheme. ■

Grain characteristics of cultivated and off-types of rice in Central Luzon, Philippines.

Farmers thought that the off-types had arisen from crosses with other cultivars, by degeneration from continuous use of the same cultivar, and from seed mixtures.

Competition and possible preharvest shattering of off-types of rice reduce yield and contaminate harvested rice, decreasing both grade and quality. Control is difficult and expensive. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.